

ASSESSMENT OF PARTICULATE MATTER IN INDUSTRIAL AREA OF ELEME COMMUNITIES OF RIVERS STATE, NIGER DELTA, NIGERIA

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Abstract: The study assessed levels of Particulate matter in Eleme communities of Rivers State, Nigeria. The work was carried out between 27th September and 24th of November, 2019, using a purposive sampling technique. Data was analysed statistically by Pearson correlation and Chi-square test method. The parameters tested were PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀. CW-HAT 20 handheld portable counter was used, while meteorological parameters tested were Temperature, Relative Humidity, Wind speed, and direction. The result showed that PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations were 93.40 and 64.30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ respectively. PM₁₀ was within the NESREA limit of 150 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, while PM_{2.5} was above NESREA limit of 40.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The elevated values of PM_{2.5} could be attributed to emissions from industries, vehicles, and soot particles from illegal refining and highway clouds of dust in the area. Akpajo community was identified as the most air polluted community which could be due to proximity to the petrochemical industry, the highway that experiences gridlock, and wind transportation action, While Aleto, where petrochemical industry is located, was identified as the less air polluted community. Particulate matter level increases from September through to November which could be attributed to cessation of rainfall that could have diluted the PM. The study suggests that industries should seek alternative sources of energy, efficient traffic management systems should be instituted, and public enlightenment on the advantages of tree planting to reduce the health effects of PM on the residents of the study area.

Keywords: Particulate matter, Industrial area, Automobile emissions, Eleme community.

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria started oil exploration of its oil and gas, and other natural resources in the 1970s. As a result, it has experienced an escalation in its population growth, urbanization, and industrialization together with an increase in motorization and energy use. The environment today has become contaminated, undesirable, and harmful to man's habitat following the pollution of air (Oguname, 2016). An air pollutant is a substance in the air that has adverse effects on humans and the ecosystem. Indoor air pollutants and urban air quality are listed as two of the world's worst toxic pollution problems and about two million people die prematurely from the effects of polluted air, every year (WHO, 2014). The gaseous combination of solid and liquid particles suspended in air is known as Particulate Matter. (WHO, 2013; Adams, Greenbaum, Shaikh, Van and Russell, 2015; Istiqomah and Marleni., 2020). Air pollution is primarily caused by the emission of harmful substances into the atmosphere, including particulate matter (PM), Nitrogen dioxide, Sulfur dioxide, Ozone, and Volatile organic compounds, among others. These pollutants are released from various sources such as industrial facilities, transportation, agriculture, and energy production (Lanzar, Sanja, Zvonimir, Heidi, and Goran, 2023). According to a recent University of Chicago study on the Air Quality Life Index, particulate pollution

reduces the worldwide average lifespan by an estimated value of 1.8 years for every individual. Thus, making it the world's leading killer (Greenstone and Fan, 2018). Several studies have shown that high wind speed promotes the attenuation of atmospheric pollutants, whereas low wind speed promotes the accumulation of pollutants. The air movement is determined by wind speed and direction. The greater the wind speed, the greater the dispersion of pollution and subsequent dilution. Direction is also vital in determining where the polluted air moves and thus controls the downwind or/and upward impacted areas. Temperature, on the other hand, influences atmospheric chemical reactions and tends to stagnate air mass formation, which leads to a higher concentration of particulates formed, and vice versa at higher temperatures (Onaiwu, Okuo, Jonathan and Omorogiuwa, 2022).

In China, Lifao, Jia, Wei, Pu, and Shaoba, (2014) found that PM₁₀ is undoubtedly the most important pollutant in Chinese cities. In the all-city average, the frequencies of days having PM₁₀ as the key pollutant are 76.1%, 73.4%, and 71.5% in 2001, 2006, and 2011, respectively. The meteorology of a location has a significant impact on the quality of air in that area. Thus, meteorological variables such as air temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, wind direction, atmospheric pressure, ultraviolet radiation, and solar radiation have significantly influenced the rapid diffusion, dilution, and accumulation of atmospheric fine particle pollution (Liu and Cui 2014).

In Nigeria, Meseka, Akpoola, Falaiye, and Targema (2022) study on temperature and relative humidity in Abuja and Kano showed that, during the dry season in both locations, the monthly average of PM_{1.0}, PM_{2.5}, and PM_{10.0} surpasses the WHO 24-hour standard limit. Since both locations are the two major areas in the Northern part of Nigeria, where the population is increasing rapidly, this can be attributed to excessive pollution and an increase in car emissions, while in the wet season, the results were within the WHO limit. Similarly, from Benin, Onaiwu, Okuo, Jonathan, and Omorogiuwa (2022) discovered that some meteorological parameters significantly influence total PM levels. PM is discharged into the air by a variety of natural and man-made sources (Miranda and Tomaz, 2008). They are released from smoke, dirt, dust, or construction sites, while others are formed in the atmosphere due to complicated chemical reactions, such as Nitrogen oxides and Sulfur (iv) oxide—pollutants produced by factories and power plants. PM emissions are said to be causing increased air pollution around the globe due to their tremendous influence on man and the environment (Duan, Chan, Fang and Su, 2015).

PM_{2.5} enters the blood stream as well as the lungs. It causes inflammation and harm, such as respiratory sickness, a lowered immune response, congenital defects, and diabetes, among other things (Feng, Bei, Huang, Cao, Zhang, Zhou, and Li, 2016). Studies have found that suspended particulate matter (SPM) has some negative environmental effects, such as reduced visibility (Haze), changes in atmospheric properties, the formation of fog and precipitation, damage to vegetation and materials, and climate change due to changes in solar radiation, wind distribution, and temperature in particular (Masiol and Harrison, (2014). Also, depending on the season, it was evident that some meteorological parameters influence total PM levels. (Onaiwu *et al*, 2022). Meteorological variables influence the dispersion, dilution, and accumulation of atmospheric fine particle pollution. Therefore, there is need to explore these variables, and their effects on PM in an emerging industrial area such as Eleme.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Clean air is a basic requirement for human health and well-being. Contamination of air arising from anthropogenic inputs have been a global concern due to health effects associated with it. High levels of gases and PMs tend to pollute the atmosphere as they cause harmful effects on the environment and human health. Furthermore, it was believed that polluted air killed more people worldwide than AIDS, malaria, breast cancer, or tuberculosis. Eleme is an emerging industrial area with refineries, petrochemical industry, cement packaging factory, oil servicing companies and a sea port. There were complaints on air pollution frequently observed by the residents. The observation includes hazy and dusty atmosphere, with black particles settling on cars, clothes, roofs, and black stains from nostrils when cleaned with a handkerchief. It was also marred by difficulty in breathing, wheezing and sneezing. The soot problem, according to experts suggested pollution by incomplete combustion of fossil fuels, bio-mass, burning of tires, and the illegal artisanal refining operations within the area. Environmental experts warned that it could pose a serious threat to human health, agriculture and climate. It is therefore necessary, to assess the level of PM concentration and possible mitigation solutions to the discharges, to minimize their impact on human health. This consideration necessitated the need for the study in the Eleme community.

1.3 Objective of the study

The main objective is the Assessment of Particulate Matter in the Industrial Area of Eleme Communities of Rivers State, Niger Delta, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to;

- i. Evaluate the Particulate Matter (PM) levels in the atmospheric environment of the study area
- ii. Determine the effects of some meteorological variables on the Particulate Matter (PM) concentration of the study area

1.4 Hypotheses of the study

- i. Particulate Matter (PM) levels have no significant effect on the atmospheric environment of the study area.
- ii. Some meteorological variables have no significant effect on Particulate Matter (PM) concentration in the study area.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Background meteorological factors, i.e. wind speed, wind direction, temperature, atmospheric stability, mixing height, etc., significantly impact the concentration of pollutants in a certain area (Das, Sarkar, Mandal, Saha, Sand and Gosh, 2021). Wang, Cao, Tie, Wang, Li, Hu Zhao, and Xu, (2015) argued that air pollutant concentrations rely on direct emissions and the quantity of gaseous precursors, which are NO₂, SO₂, CO₂, and PM_{2.5}, as well as meteorological variables. Similarly, Zhou, Yu, Gu, Wu, Wang, Yue, Gao, Lei, and Ge, (2020) stated that meteorological conditions affect the dispersion of air pollutants and control atmospheric pollution on a moderately abrupt continuance scale. Akinfolarin, *et al*, (2018) concluded that 'some emerging industrial areas could be responsible for the indiscriminate emissions of the obnoxious gases. According to He *et al*, (2017), more than 70% of the daily air pollutant absorption in China could be attributed to meteorological conditions, while Chan *et al*, (2013) documented that there is no clear linear relationship between the air pollutant concentration due to chemical transformation and meteorological parameters such as relative humidity, temperature, and atmospheric pressure.

In 2010, the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) classified suspended PMs as group 1 carcinogens that are proven to be carcinogenic to humans (Marzouni, *et al*, (2017). Furthermore, there is a higher risk of mortality among those who are frequently exposed to PMs. EPA, (2012) described constituents

of PM, which include soot, smoke, dust, dirt, and liquid droplets. It is classified primarily based on its size, known as its aerodynamic diameter. Fine particles (PM_{2.5}) have a diameter of less than 2.5 μ m, whereas coarse particles (PM₁₀) have a diameter of 10 to 2.5 μ m. PM_{2.5} particles include soot and smoke from combustion, whereas SPM particles include dust, pollen, mist, mold, fungi, and other microorganisms with PM_{2.5} inclusive. The concentration of PM differs according to, but is not limited to the following factors wind speed, precipitation, weather conditions, and RH (Ghim, 2001). Studies have uncovered that both meteorological conditions and air pollutant emissions dominate pollutant concentration trends (Zhong *et al.*, 2018). From the study of slum settlements in Lagos, Oluwaseun, Kuaanan, John, Opeyemi and Moses, (2021) stated that atmospheric pressure, relative humidity, and temperature can be contributing factors in governing air pollutant concentrations in the slum settlement of Lagos. Studies have shown that as humidity increases, PM becomes too large and can no longer remain in the atmosphere hence, began to fall a process known as dry deposition of PM (Wang and Ogawa 2015). A positive correlation of temperature with PMs was recorded indicating that as the temperature increases, PM concentration increases and vice versa (Meseke *et al.*, 2022). Similarly, Tecer *et al.*, 2008; Hernandez *et al.*, 2017) reported that increased temperature reduces SPM/TSP accumulation while rainfall reduces TSP concentrations. In their contribution to the effect of temperature on weather, Akhilesh *et al.*, (2015) and Ukhurebor *et al.*, (2017) opined that Temperature is a very critical factor in determining the weather; because it influences or controls other elements such as precipitation, humidity, clouds, atmospheric and pressure. Its measurement tends to have a great influence on other parameters and their applications. PMs are removed through wet deposition instead of gravitational settling. The particles are captured by water droplets in the atmosphere and removed by a process called washout if insoluble. The main source for washout is impaction and interception, where a rain droplet removes particles in the layer below the cloud on its way down to the surface. If the particles are soluble, they go into solution with rainwater (Ede and Edokpa, 2015).

Several studies have found that suspended particulate matter (SPM) has some negative environmental effects, such as reduced visibility (Haze), changes in atmospheric properties, the formation of fog and precipitation, damage to vegetation and materials, and climate change due to changes in solar radiation, wind distribution, and temperature in particular (Masiol and Harrison, 2014; Onuorah *et al.*, 2019). PM₁₀ particulate pollution is one of the major problems in the major cities of the developed world and has become a serious and worsening situation in rapidly growing cities in the developing world, especially in Africa due to urbanization and industrialization (Dotse *et al.*, 2012). Research has also shown that high concentrations of fine particulates (PM_{2.5}) cause respiratory problems, cerebrovascular disease, ischemic heart disease, and lung cancer (Burnett *et al.*, 2014).

3. METHODOLOGY

Description of Study Area

Keys:

- ▲ Sample Area
- Control Sample

Figure 1, shows the study area and sampled communities

Source; Google map

The study area is Eleme Local Government (LG) area in River's state, Niger Delta, Nigeria. It lies within Lat. $4^{\circ}49'25''$ and $N4^{\circ}43'66''$ North of the Equator and Long. $7^{\circ}5'10''$ and $E7^{\circ}9'29''$ East of Greenwich Meridian. It is bordered to the North by Obio-Akpor and Oyibo LGAs, to the East by Tai, south by Okrika and Ogu-Bolo LGAs, and the West by Port-Harcourt city LGA. It had a population of 190,884 people according to NPC (2006) and is projected to be 273,500 (2022), with a total land mass of 138 km^2 . Eleme people are one of the various ethnic indigenous groups of people found in the Niger Delta of Nigeria. They live in 10 communities in clusters about 20km from Port-Harcourt. The major occupation of the Eleme people from ancient times has remained farming, and the primary crops they produce include yams, cocoyam, cassava, sugarcane and pumpkin. Farmlands are usually in large blocs that are commonly cultivated each year through ownership of properly demarcated sections of land, vested in each family. (Obenade, Ekwuga, Henry and Okpiliya, 2020). The study area is one of the LGAs considered as upland in River's state.

Eleme communities are divided into two major administrative blocs or political units: the Nchia bloc with six clans (Alesa, Akpajo, Agbonchia, Alode, Aletto) and the Odido bloc (Onne, Ebubu, Ete'o and Ekporo). Each unit has numerous sub-communities (Obenade, *et al*, 2020). Eleme is an emerging industrial area with industries such as two Refineries, a foremost fertilizer plant in West Africa (Notore, formerly known as NAFCON), a seaport, with many other companies located in Onne such as Panalpina, Intels, Dangote cement, Federal Lighter Terminal and Federal Ocean Terminal.

Sample and Data Collection

The study area consists of ten Eleme communities; however, samples were purposively taken from six due to safety concerns and inadequate equipment. The six sampled sites were Alesa, Alode, Aletto, Agbonchia, Akpajo, and Onne. The control sample point was in Sakpenwa, Tai LGA of the state. The design approach was experimental. Data were collected from instruments in situ and recorded. Two teams were used. The first team covered Akpajo, Aletto, and Alesa. The second team covered Alode, Onne, Agbonchia, and the control sample site. The samples were taken in the morning between 0800 and 1000 hours and in the evening between 1600 and 1800 hours. Samples were taken five times between 27th September and 24th November 2019. Global Positioning System (GPS) was utilized in taking the coordinates of each sampling location. The teams took readings from instruments as allocated, and the instruments were turned off after each analysis. Collected data were tested by using the hypothesis formulated in conformity with the objective of the study.

All equipment were calibrated before measurement. At any given location, a CW HAT-20 handheld portable counter was used for PM10 and PM2.5. A cup anemometer was used to measure wind speed and direction, and A multi-purpose digital Kestrel digital weather tracker (model 4500) was used to monitor temperature and RH. It is a real-time instrument with instant weather reports. Then the detected PMs and meteorological parameters were calculated and recorded. The temperature was measured in 0°C, humidity in %, wind speed in m/s, PMs in µg/m³, and wind direction in cardinal points. It was ensured that sample points did not have any physical obstruction or interferences. Physical obstructions such as trees and buildings were situated far away from the sample points.

Table 1: Sampled Locations in Eleme Communities

Location	Coordinate	
Akpajo	N4 ⁰ 49'25"	E7 ⁰ 11'21"
Aletto	N4 ⁰ 48'46"	E7 ⁰ 10'52"
Alode	N4 ⁰ 46'45"	E7 ⁰ 12'01"
Alesa	4 ⁰ 56'53"N	E7 ⁰ 11'50"
Agbonchia	4 ⁰ 47'47"N	E7 ⁰ 12'70"
Onne	4 ⁰ 63'66"N	E7 ⁰ 14'49"
Sakpenwa	4 ⁰ 43'05"N	E7 ⁰ 15'46"

Source: GPS Coordinate

RESULT

The results obtained were from the six Eleme communities as shown in appendix 1 and figure 2. However, the mean result is recorded in Table 3 and compared with the NESREA Standard. Figure 3 shows the

relationship between meteorological parameters and PM concentration at different sampled periods. The control sample had PM concentrations within NESREA's maximum permissible limit.

Table 2: Eleme Community Ambient Air Quality

Parameter	Eleme (Mean)	Control
Temp (0C)	31.12	29.8
Rel. Humidity (%)	75.70	91.3
Wind speed (m/s)	1.72	3.2
Wind Direction	NE	SE
PM10 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	93.40	21.10
PM2.5 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	64.30	15.10

Source: Fieldwork, (2019)

Table 3: Showing Result and NESREA Standard

Parameter	Eleme (Mean)	NESREA Standard 2021
Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	31.12	Ambient
Rel. Humidity (%)	75.70	NS
Wind speed (m/s)	1.72	NS
Wind Direction	NE	NA
PM10 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	93.40	150 for 24hourly
PM2.5 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	64.30	40 for 24hourly

Source: Field work (2019) and NESREA Standard (2021)

Figure 2: Eleme Communities Ambient Air Quality

Figure 3: Showing the Relationship between meteorological parameters and PM concentration at Different sampled Periods

4 DATA ANALYSIS

Discussion of Findings

Temperature- It is defined as the range of degrees of hotness and coolness of the body. It affects or controls other components such as dew point, RH, air vapors, and atmospheric air pressure (Geerts, 2003). The temperature range for the study area was between 28.5 and 33.6⁰C. During the study period, the mean

temperature was 31.6⁰C. Akpajo, a village in the community had the lowest temperature of 28.5⁰C, while Onne had the highest temperature (33.6⁰C), which could be due to industrial and Sea Port activities in the area. Temporarily, Figure 3 shows that the highest temperature was recorded in September (32.4⁰C) during the wet season, while November 11 recorded the lowest temperature of 29.67⁰C, which could be due to ushering in of harmattan wind. The temperature was within range when we consider the work of Nkin (2023), who pointed out, that the range of temperature within Eleme study zones was between 28.10 and 34.60⁰C. Ogunjobi, Kim, Adedokun, and Ryu, (2002) observed that convective clouds are mainly responsible for the marked reduction of intensity of solar radiation during the wet season. Although Oyediran *et al*, (2012) reported that PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ had weak and positive correlation coefficients with air temperature, Jayamurugan, Kumaravel, and Chockalingam, (2013), observed that temperature has a positive correlation to the concentration of PM but a negative correlation to RH.

Relative Humidity – The range was between 71.0 and 83.10%, while the mean value in the study area was 75.70%. Aleto had 83.10%, while Agbonchia had 71.0% (Figure and appendix 1). 85.17% of RH was observed on 9th October, being the highest, while 58.67% was observed on November 24 (Figure 3), which could be attributed to the commencement of the dry season. The result indicated that the study area was humid during the study period. According to Jayamurugan, *et al*, (2013), the relationship between RH and temperature simply shows that they are conversely proportional. That means, if the temperature increases, it will lead to a decrease in RH, thus the air will become drier, whereas when the temperature decreases, the air will become wet, which means the RH will increase. In his work on temperature and RH in Delhi, India, Vaishali *et al*, (2023) concluded that PM_{2.5} concentration had a strong negative correlation with temperature during the high humid conditions. Meseke (2022), studied the PM and RH relationship, and concluded using results from Pearson correlation analysis, that PMs and RH have substantial negative correlations indicating that as RH rises in either location, PM mass concentration would decrease as well. However, a relatively high correlation existed between PMs and temperature for both locations. The health impacts are either direct or indirect in urban areas (Akinfolarin *et al.*, 2017. Humidity in the atmosphere affects the temperature, wind speed, and concentration of PMs in an environment.

Wind speed. The mean wind speed in the study area was 1.72m/s, while the range was 1.41-1.86m/s from Agbonchia and Akpajo respectively (Figure 2 and appendix 1). Temporarily, November 24th had the highest wind speed of 1.97m/s which could be linked to the commencement of the dry season. Singh *et al*, (2022), found that there is a strong negative correlation between PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ with ambient air temperature and wind speed. Teerachal *et al*, (2023), supported this by observing, that high PM_{2.5} was mostly associated with low speed. Abhishek, Keener, and Yang (2010), opined that the correlation between wind speed and the concentration of air pollutants suggests that, wind speed above 2.0 m/s is capable of diluting or reducing the level of air pollutants in an area. According to Ukpebor *et al.* (2010) and Yorkor *et al.* (2017), low wind speed, high temperature, and low humidity in the dry season reduce the rate of dispersion of air pollutants, thus increasing ground concentration of some pollutants during the dry season and vice versa. Similar findings by Trivedi, Ali, and Beig, (2014) in Delhi concluded that PM concentration shows seasonality, and it is attributed mainly to meteorology. Seasonal variations are primarily determined by wind and the wind is responsible transportation of PM, fog, and vapour. The above explanation could explain the reason for the high mean PMs in the study area, 93.40 and 64.30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ respectively. In Nigeria, the range of wind speed

is about 2m/s to about 4m/s, with the highest average speeds of 3.5m/s and 7.5m/s in southern and northern Nigeria respectively (Fegbenle and Karayiannis, 1994). In general, wind transports air PMs away from their sources, causing them to disperse. The higher the wind speed, the more particles are dispersed and the lower their concentration. Low wind speed promotes the formation of smog phenomena in big cities. (Godish *et al*, 2015). This assertion could have been the reason for low PM₁₀ and high PM_{2.5}, with a mean wind speed of 1.72m/s in Eleme, Niger Delta.

PM₁₀ –Meteorological conditions determine the behavior and fate of atmospheric particulates after being released from the source. Physical sizes depend on the aerodynamic dimension of the particulates (Oyediran, Ogundele, Felix, and Olusegun, 2012). Coarse particles, such as PM₁₀ do not remain airborne for a long time and their spatial impact is typically limited because they tend to deposit on the ground downwind of emission sources. Particles of different sizes react differently in the air. (Rose, Hilda, Olayinka, and Olumide 2021). PM can stay in the atmosphere for a few seconds or it can remain suspended for years. Large-sized particles spend less time in a suspended state for a few seconds, on the other hand, small-sized particles remain suspended for years (Pokhrel *et al.*, 2015). The highest concentration of PM₁₀ in the study area was observed in Akpajo with 134.90 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, while the lowest concentration was recorded in Aleto with 69.70 g/m^3 .

The mean PM₁₀ concentration was 93.40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (Figure 2 and appendix 1). The maximum permissible limit (MPL) by NESREA is 150 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for 24 hours on average. The low value of PM₁₀ observed in the study area may not be unconnected with the size of the particles which could not remain air born for long and could be due to the activity of wind transport that might have transported the particles to other locations (Rose *et al* 2021 and Pokhrel *et al.*, (2015). Petrochemical company is located within Aleto, however, Aleto had the lowest PM₁₀ concentration, while the highest level was observed in Akpajo. This could be linked to the trajectory movement of air from the source of pollution to other locations, flare stack position, height, and rainfall intensity. The high PM₁₀ value in Akpajo can be traced to the proximity to highways with high vehicular movement and a busy road junction. To support this claim, A study was carried out in 9 countries and 16 provinces in Europe by He, Chen, Wang, Rangognio, and Colin, (2018), the concentration of PM_{2.5} ranged from 8.1 to 43.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Research by Akuro, (2012); and Ukpebor and Okolo, (2002) has also confirmed that the level of suspended PM in cities especially in their industrial zones is high due to wind-blown dust from the roads, emissions from machinery in the industry, and industrial vehicles. From Figure 3, PM₁₀ was highest on November 11th with 123.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, when rainfall had started ceding. With this, the rainfall intensity was not enough to have scavenged the PM₁₀ in the atmosphere. The lowest value was observed on September 27th, 2019 as 54.17 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. High pollutant concentrations contribute to illnesses and respiratory diseases in urban dwellers. Epidemiological studies have reported a positive association between daily mean PM concentrations with an aerodynamic diameter >10 μm (PM₁₀), 2.5 μm (PM_{2.5}), and 1 μm (PM_{1.0}) and increased mortality and morbidity ascribed to respiratory and cardiovascular defects (Dominici *et al.*, 2006). While PM₁₀ has been associated with respiratory issues, the focus on lung cancer morbidity often involves the finer particles, particularly PM_{2.5}. (Hamza, Guha, Cohen, Samet and Saldiva, 2014). Inhaling excessive amounts of PM which can be blown over great distances by the wind and then settle in the ground, water, or in the air we breathe, can be hazardous to both sensitive and non-sensitive persons (Meseke, 2022).

PM_{2.5}- It is a fine particle of aerodynamic size of 2.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and below. The mean concentration in the study area was 64.30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, and the range was between 51.20 and 94.10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The concentration of PM_{2.5} was not

steady in 6 different Eleme communities. This could be traced to its fine particle size that could not stay in the atmosphere for a long period before settling on surfaces or could be transported to other places. The impact of finer particles are higher than coarse particles (Araujo *et al.*, 2014). Akpajo recorded the highest PM_{2.5} with 94.10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, while Aleto, a community that harbours Petrochemical, had 51.20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, being the lowest PM_{2.5} level in the study area. The MPL for PM_{2.5} by NESREA is 40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for 24 hourly averages. This implies that the PM_{2.5} value is above the NESREA limit of 40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Although the petrochemical is situated in Aleto, the height of the flare stack and wind trajectory action could have transported the particles to Akpajo. Alesa village harbors a refinery and is a commercial nerve center of the study area. A highway transverses through Akpajo, Aleto, and Alesa as seen in Figure 1, bush burning, ashes, and clouds of dust emanating from the destruction of bunkering barges and canoes by the military, activities of artisanal refining operations and farming activities could have raised the PM_{2.5} concentration in Akpajo. Aleto, a village that harbours petrochemical had a PM_{2.5} value of 51.2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, the lowest in the study area. Rainfall intensity, wind activities and topography of Aleto could have influenced the PM concentration. In Thailand, Teerachal, *et al.*, (2023) observed that PM_{2.5} is negatively correlated with humidity. Oyediran *et al.*, (2012) reported PM concentration in Ile-Ife as 25.37 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 37.15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ respectively. The studies by Singh, Kumar, and Jain, (2021) also stated that the concentration of PM_{2.5} in any given location is negatively correlated with meteorological parameters like ambient temperature, wind, dew point, and wind gust, while it is positive with relative humidity. PM affects the environment as it contributes to greenhouse gases National Emission Standards, (1999). It affects human health and can easily reach the deepest parts of the lungs, leading to respiratory ailments. Dominici *et al.*, (2006) observed in epidemiological studies of PM, reported that there is a positive association between daily mean PM concentrations with an aerodynamic diameter >10 μm (PM₁₀), 2.5 μm (PM_{2.5}), and 1 μm (PM_{1.0}) and increased mortality and morbidity ascribed to respiratory and cardiovascular defects). Araujo *et al.*, (2014) opined that the impact of fine particles are higher than those of larger particles.

Wind direction – the wind directions observed within the study area were NE and SW. However, NE was the dominant wind direction. SW wind direction was dominant in the control site. Wind direction plays a major role in emission source height and magnitude of emission from the source (David and Moses, 2017). The observation is supported by Sinna, (2021), that wind can move air pollution away from its source, locally and globally. it also accounts for air pollution disparities according to prevailing wind. It can pinpoint pollution sources allowing for informed decisions to protect human health. This assertion was demonstrated in PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} results shown in Figure 3. Petrochemical company is located in the Aleto community and has a flare stack. However, the pollution-receiving community was Akpajo, which has a common boundary with Aleto. PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations from Aleto were 60.70 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 51.20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ respectively, while Akpajo had 134.90 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for PM₁₀ and 94.10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for PM_{2.5}. Although Akinfolarin *et al.*, (2018) asserted that meteorological data obtained (except Oxygen) were below the detectable level and that no industrial activity was contributing to the emission of soot in the Port-Harcourt area. However, Nkin (2023) revealed that human activities, particularly industries and agricultural activities were the major sources of air pollution in Eleme areas, outskirts of Port-Harcourt. Wind direction determines which type of air mass usually moves over an area.

Toxicity Assessment - Ayodele *et al.* (2016) explained that toxicity potential (TP) is a calculated toxic equivalent that is useful in determining the potential harm that air pollution particles from different places

may cause to human health. Using the following formula, we determined the TP associated with PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ in Eleme as the study area:

$TP = CP/SP$; where SP is the air pollution standard and CP is the measured pollutant concentration. The TP value should therefore be less than 1. A region where there is a high concentration of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} poses a health danger to the local population. This type of locality is known by a TP score greater than one. Results from the calculation showed that PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} had a Toxicity Potential of 0.62 and 1.61 respectively. It implies that the TP of PM_{2.5} was high and attention of authority must be drawn to this reality.

Summary of Findings

PM₁₀ analyzed in the study area was within the NESREA limit, while PM_{2.5} was high when compared with the NESREA limit for 24 hourly average. Fine particles size could stay in the atmosphere for a long period before settling on surfaces, or could easily be transported to other places due to their weight. The impact of finer particles are higher than coarse particles. It affects human health and can easily reach the deepest parts of the lungs, leading to respiratory ailments. Therefore, there is a need for concern by authority. The most polluted community in Eleme according to the study of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} was Akpajo, which could be attributed to the trajectory of dust plumule from highways, air transportation of PMs, wind direction, and location of highway that traverses the community. Wind speed was generally moderate, average of 1.72m/s and the dominant wind direction was NE. The less polluted community was Aleto, where the petrochemical company is located. The reason could be due to the height of the flaring stack, trajectory movement of wind, and concentration of emitted pollutants from the sources. The study has shown a slightly negative correlation between RH and PMs, and a strong positive relationship exists between temperature and RH. Similarly, wind speed has shown a slightly positive correlation with temperature. Wind speed increases with time from Sept 27 to Nov 24, except in Oct 9 when it declined to 1.11m/s. PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} generally increased in concentration from September to November 2019. while RH showed a decreasing order.

5. Conclusion

The study showed that PM₁₀ concentration is within the NESREA limit, while PM_{2.5} is higher than the NESREA limit. The toxicity potential of PM_{2.5} is 1.61, which exhibits that attention must be given to the sources of particles for mitigation. Fine particles when inhaled can reach the deepest part of the human respiratory system causing ailments such as bronchitis and Asthma. The study concludes that Meteorological parameters play a significant role in the concentration of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}. The study has identified Akpajo as the hot spot area in the study, with high PMs associated with the possibility of deleterious effects on human health. There is a need to address this concern.

Recommendations

- There should be improved traffic control management within Eleme axis.
- Plantation of trees in the Eleme community could help in the reduction of dust on other surfaces
- The authority should ensure that industries within the Eleme community do not exceed the required concentration limit for gas emissions.
- Industries should commence looking for alternative sources of power generation, fossil fuel is not environmentally friendly, and clean air initiatives should be adopted.

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Appendix 1

Table 4: Eleme Communities Ambient Air Quality

Parameter	AKPAJO	ALETO	ONNE	ALODE	AGBONCHIA	ALESA
Temp (OC)	28.5	30.0	33.6	32.3	31.2	31.1
Rel. Humidity (%)	80.7	83.1	74.1	74.3	71.1	71.7
Wind speed (m/s)	1.86	1.59	1.50	1.72	1.41	1.68
PM10 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	134.90	69.70	83.60	88.50	83.30	121.40
PM2.5 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	94.10	51.20	52.90	59.80	59.90	81.80

Source: Field Work, 2019